

Network Resource Management for Unified 6G Network: The UNITY-6G Approach

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Abstract—It is expected that network resource management will continue to play a key role in 6G networks. While previous generation mobile networks have already addressed network resource management, they fall short in addressing the complex and integrated infrastructure of 6G, which includes crucial aspects such as intelligence, trust, privacy, sustainability and scalability. This paper presents the UNITY-6G architecture, a unified framework for end-to-end resource management across integrated terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks. UNITY-6G leverages a multi-layered design composed of physical infrastructure, network resource abstraction, service-based control, intelligent agentic AI, and blockchain-enabled security mechanisms. The proposed framework enables dynamic orchestration through distributed AI agents (local, regional, global) that adaptively coordinate resource allocation and optimization tasks. Service-Based Architecture (SBA) components provide modular and programmable control of core network functions, while blockchain technologies ensure trust, transparency, and secure auditing of operations. The architecture supports emerging use cases such as immersive Extended Reality (XR), energy management and industrial automation by aligning network intelligence with application requirements.

Index Terms—integrated networks, 6G, resource management

I. INTRODUCTION

The next generation of wireless networks, 6G, requires intelligent, scalable and secure management of heterogeneous network resources to support diverse and latency-sensitive applications. In this paper, we provide a blueprint for building intelligent, secure, and future-proof 6G infrastructures relying on UNITY-6G architecture¹. Fig. 1 provides a framework that integrates multiple technological enablers — including agentic Artificial Intelligence (AI), Service Based Architecture (SBA) and blockchain auditing— in a multi-layered UNITY-6G architecture. It supports dynamic orchestration of Terrestrial Network (TN) and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) resources to enable advanced 6G use cases such as streaming operations, industrial control, energy management and immersive Extended Reality (XR) applications at the top application layer. The blockchain and security layer introduces a decentralized approach to trust and auditing through blockchain as a service, smart contracts, chainlink integration and blockchain-enabled auditing mechanisms. The intelligence layer is powered by agentic AI, which consists of local, regional and global AI agents that coordinate via multi-agent systems and feedback loops. These agents provide continuous insights and adaptive control signals to the underlying layers. The control layer,

structured as a SBA, includes dynamic microservices and core network functions such as Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF) and Policy Control Function (PCF) that enable scalable and modular control of network resources. The network resource abstraction layer decouples the physical infrastructure from the service logic and manages resources such as spectrum, computing power, storage and network slicing. The foundation is the physical infrastructure layer, which integrates both TN and NTN components, including Radio Access Network (RAN), core network units and nodes such as satellites. The layered architecture illustrates both the vertical orchestration of resources and the horizontal integration of foundational technologies that enable intelligent, secure and adaptive resource management for 6G networks.

Fig. 1: Generic architecture of UNITY-6G for intelligent network resource management.

II. RESOURCE MANAGEMENT WITH AGENTIC AI

In the context of 6G networks, the increasing complexity and heterogeneity of resources require a shift from rule-based orchestration to adaptive and autonomous decision-making. Agentic AI introduces a paradigm in which distributed intelligent agents, e.g. local, regional and global, collaborate

¹Online: <https://unity-6g.eu/>, Available: April 2025.

to manage network resources in real time [1]. These agents are embedded in different network segments and enable context-aware decision making, proactive resource allocation, and dynamic policy adaptation based on environmental feedback. Local agents can work at the edge of the network to perform latency-sensitive tasks, while regional agents can aggregate insights and optimize resources across domains. Global agents on the other hand provide strategic oversight and enforce long-term optimization goals and consistent policies. By coordinating multiple agents, these AI entities learn from historical data and real-time telemetry, enabling self-organization and self-healing capabilities. The agentic AI framework can ensure scalability, adaptability and resilience, making it a key enabler for intelligent resource management in 6G networks.

III. RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN SBA

SBA adopts a microservices-based design where the different Network Functions (NFs) (e.g., AMF, SMF, PCF) communicate using web-based Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), typically RESTful APIs over HTTP/2, avoiding former monolithic or point-to-point architectures with dedicated telecom-specific protocols. In such way, dynamic discovery and registration of resources, independent scaling and updating of each NF, easier integration with third party apps (e.g., NEF-AF, Common API Framework (CAPIF) [2]), faster deployment and multi-vendor integration can be achieved. Being proved effective for the 5G Core and given the heterogeneity network resources, this paradigm seems suitable for next generation mobile network evolution. Under such context, UNITY-6G focuses on the SBA principles to evolve them and develop a system integrating different resources belonging to Open RAN, transport, satellite systems and AI/ML domains to provide end-to-end service delivery across the edge-cloud continuum. Based on the use of a dedicated service bus, UNITY-6G architecture will dynamically accommodate services with diverse requirements in a reliable and scalable way. The available discovery service and registry capabilities will facilitate the communication between the consumer requests and the specific instances of available heterogeneous resources mentioned previously to build flexible, and maintainable applications and services.

IV. RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN TN-NTNs

The convergence of TN and NTNs in 6G brings unprecedented opportunities and challenges for end-to-end resource management. Intelligent resource management in this integrated environment requires a holistic approach that considers the dynamic characteristics of heterogeneous infrastructures, including ground-based RANs, core networks, low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites or geostationary satellites (GEO). UNITY-6G manages this complexity by utilising AI-driven orchestration to enable adaptive resource provisioning in areas with widely varying latency, coverage and mobility constraints. The architecture ensures seamless interoperability between TN and NTNs nodes by abstracting the heterogeneity of physical resources and enabling real-time coordination through agentic

AI and service-based control mechanisms. Intelligent scheduling, spectrum sharing and load balancing are performed dynamically, taking into account orbital patterns, link variability and user mobility. This unified and intelligent approach to resource management enables resilient, scalable and globally connected services and positions the integrated TN/NTN as the cornerstone of the 6G infrastructure.

V. RESOURCE MANAGEMENT WITH BLOCKCHAIN

The secure and efficient management of dynamic interactions between multiple parties is beyond the capabilities of traditional centralized trust models, creating a need for alternative approaches to enforce contracts and ensure transparency. In light of such challenges, the NGMN (Next Generation Mobile Networks) Alliance emphasizes the importance of incorporating *trustworthiness* by design into 6G [3] advocating for decentralized systems such as blockchain to meet transparency, privacy, reliability, resilience and security requirements. Blockchain's decentralized and immutable ledger enables operators to transparently lease or share surplus network capacity, automate Service Level Agreement (SLA) enforcement, and enable secure transactions without relying on intermediaries. For example, during a major international sporting event, operators from different administrative domains could use blockchain-based smart contracts to dynamically lease excess network resources to each other, ensuring real-time SLA compliance, automated settlement, and trustworthy multi-domain collaboration.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents UNITY-6G, a unified architecture for intelligent and secure network resource management tailored for the next generation of 6G networks. By integrating agentic AI, service-based control, blockchain-powered security and the convergence of TN and NTNs infrastructures, UNITY-6G provides a scalable and adaptable framework that meets the diverse requirements of future applications. The multi-layer design of the architecture enables cross-domain coordination, real-time resource optimization and trustworthy operation, supporting a wide range of use cases — from immersive media to autonomous systems. Through intelligent orchestration and distributed decision making, UNITY-6G paves the way to a resilient, self-optimising and context-aware 6G ecosystem.

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